

Revealing the Surfaces of Stars with Interferometric Imaging

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5 July 2022

Basic Interferometer

Interferometric Imaging

- Surfaces imaged directly as appear on sky
- Advantages
 - Determines orientation on sky, inclination
 - Accurately maps feature locations
 - No fundamental limit to resolution
- Disadvantages
 - Requires large stars
 - Requires bright stars
 - Limited baseline lengths

Light-curve Inversion

- Inhomogeneities rotate in and out of view causing variability
- Advantages
 - Applied to any star
 - Constrains spot longitude
 - Requires little data
- Disadvantages
 - Poor latitude constraints
 - No inclination constraints
 - Only detected rotation modulation

Doppler Imaging

- Inhomogeneities rotate in and out of view seen as distortions in absorption lines
- Advantages
 - Constrains spot latitude
 - Constrains spot longitude
- Disadvantages
 - Requires high SNR, high-resolution spectra
 - Requires good phase coverage
 - Applied to rapidly-rotating stars

Interferometric Surface Imaging

- Each pixel on the surface of a rotating star can be changed to fit multi-epoch data
- More robust than imaging single snapshots
- Analogous to technique used in Doppler imaging

ESO's Very Large Telescope Interferometer

Georgia State University's CHARA Array

Supergiant Convective Cells

Model of Red Supergiant

Image of AZ Cygni

Image reconstruction
(SQUEEZE)

Supergiant Convective Cells

Image reconstruction
(SQUEEZE)

AGB Convective Cells

π^1 Gruis

Image reconstruction (SQUEEZE)

Image reconstruction (MiRa)

Starspots: λ And (2010)

Starspots: λ And (2010)

Starspots: λ And (2010)

Model fitting

Aug 2-3

Aug 10-11

Aug 18-19

Snapshot
imaging
(SQUEEZE)

Imaging on a
sphere
(ROTIR)

Imaging on a
sphere
(SURFING)

Starspots: ζ And (2013)

2013 Imaging of ζ And (Subset A)
(Aitoff Projection)

2013 Imaging of ζ And (Subset B)
(Aitoff Projection)

All data

Imaging on a
sphere
(SURFING)

Starspots: σ Gem (2011)

Interferometric
imaging on a
sphere
(SURFING)

Doppler imaging
(INVERS7PD)

Light-curve inversion
(LI)

Starspots: σ Gem (2011)

Starspots: σ Gem (2011, 2012, & 2019)

2011

2012

Imaging on a sphere
(SURFING)

2019 **PRELIMINARY**

Imaging on a sphere
(ROTIR)

Roettenbacher et al. 2017
Roettenbacher et al. in prep.

Starspots: ζ And (2011 & 2013)

2011 Imaging of ζ And
(Aitoff Projection)

2013 Imaging of ζ And
(Aitoff Projection)

Imaging on a
sphere
(SURFING)

Starspots: ζ And (2019)

July - early August 2019

Late August - September 2019

October 2019

PRELIMINARY

Imaging on a sphere
(ROTIR)

Roettenbacher et al. in prep.

Starspots: ϵ Eri (2020)

Light-curve
inversion (LI)

Interferometric
spot model

Starspots: ϵ Eri (2020)

Light-curve inversion (LI) overlay with grid in grayscale
Interferometric spot model in color

Starspots: ϵ Eri (2020)

Starspots: ϵ Eri (2020)

Visualization: Sam Cabot

Starspots: ϵ Eri (2021)

PRELIMINARY

Imaging on a
sphere
(SURFING)

PRELIMINARY

Starspots: ϵ Eri (2021)

Summary and Future Resources

- Nearby, bright, cool stars can be directly imaged with interferometry
 - Convective cells
 - Starspots
- Imaging algorithms are robust and well-tested
- Improved resolution coming soon
 - Visible wavelength beam combiners
 - Longer baselines

ζ And

Imaging on a
sphere
(SURFING)